

Evaluation Of Armed Forces Resettlement Centres Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training on Mitigating Psycho-Economic Challenges Among Ex-Military Personels in Nigeria

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Abstract

Life after retirement has often be characteristics with poor living condition, quality of life, psychological challenges and hosts. Thus, necessitates the study on evaluation of Armed Forces Resettlement Centres Vocational and entrepreneurial training on militigating Psycho-economic challenges among Ex-military personnel in Nigeria Descriptive Survey researcher design was used. The population of the study comprised, ex-soldiers. The sample size of the study was Three hundred and thirty six (360) respondents, selected through a mono-bailing sampling technique. Three research questions were revised to seize the conduct of the study. A self-structured on developed research instruments by the researcher was used to generate data for the study and tagged, “Questionnaire on Evaluation of Armed Forces Resettlement Centres Vocational and Entrepreneurial Training on militigating Psycho-Economic challenges among Ex-military Personnel in Nigeria”. It was fashioned on 4-Likert tatting scale; Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) of 4-point; 4, 3, 2 and 1, respectively and complemented with Focus Groups Discussions (FGDS). The research instruments were validated

by two experts in Test and Measurement while, reliability was determined through test-retest methods at two weeks interval. 0.072 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data obtained on the research questions were analyzed, using descriptive statistics {simple percentages frequency counts and mean (\bar{X})}. Based on the results obtained on the study conclusions were made that the Ex-soldiers' quality of life or condition of living and psycho-economic challenges could be abated. Also, that training acquired through AFRC programmes were being put into practice. Recommendations were made therefore, that the Federal Government of Nigeria should be assisting the Ex-soldiers to source for the initial capital to start business and vocational activities as soon as, they disengage from service. Also, the duration of the programme should be extended more than a year for expensive acquisition of vocational and entrepreneurial training and host.

Keywords: Evaluation, Armed Forces, Resettlement, Training Psycho-economic, Challenges, Vocational and entrepreneurial, Ex-soldiers.

Background of the Study

Life after retirement from active government and private services has always been characterized with several challenges ranging from social, economic and psychological perspectives to many retirees, particularly in Nigeria. The implication of this is that there are no social welfare packages and late payment of gratuity to the retirees. Poor quality of life, depression, untimely death, health challenges, homelessness, redundancy and hosts are often the case with the retirees in Nigeria thus, resulting to their unethical conduct and behaviours, crimes, aggression, and hosts.

The above situation of retirees painted and depicted above is a true reflection on some of the retired ex-soldiers in Nigeria. To cope with civil life is often difficult coupled, with decent and standard condition of living for the ex-servicemen and women. Many of the retirees are already disabled which further worsened and aggravated their living condition after retirement.

The above challenges which some ex-soldiers are contending with resulted into establishment of Armed Forces Resettlement centres {AFRC} in Nigeria with a mission to be a world class training institution capable of repositioning ex-soldiers to cope with challenges of service in their post service life {AFRC, 2020}. The centres mandate is to impart vocational and entrepreneurship training for the abled ex-soldiers and those with little disability {Nigeria Armed Forces Personnel} to face the challenges of re-integrating into civil life. AFRC establishment is to promote the health and well-being and wellness of military of personnel after their retirement from active service. The importance of vocational and entrepreneurship training have been acknowledged in the contemporary Nigerian society today considering the twin problems {poverty and unemployment} high status which many Nigerians are facing with. Generally, the demand for vocational and entrepreneurship training is a global one especially, in a country like, Nigeria where there are no job opportunities, highly, accentuated by lack of industrial development and other factors. Vocational and Entrepreneurship training in a broad perspective are in line with social and economic development of individuals and the nation {EKOM, 2010:38} thus, aligns with the goals of AFRC which is equipping the ex-soldiers with skills in different vocations ranging from: woodwork, technician, craftwork, die and tyre and host. Also, skills are provided in farming activities and entrepreneurship.

Gambari (2011), stated that skills development has been man's mean of materials transformation from the earliest time. What this portends that acquisition of training in vocations and entrepreneurship withenable the acquirers to embark on some vocational activities that will result into incomes generation, wealth creation for decent living and an improved quality of life.

Erinsakin (2014), contended that training in Entrepreneurship will enable people to venture into small scale or size enterprises through acquisition of skills and values in entrepreneurial activities.

Acquisition of training in vocations and entrepreneurship thus, formed the focus of AFRC. Investigations have revealed that many ex-soldiers have into practices skills acquired through AFRC programmes observably, several studies or researchers had been conducted on AFRC vis-à-vis poverty eradication, wealth creation, incomes generation among the ex-military retired personnel. The researchers also noticed that from the numerous and avalanche researchers on AFRC, focus have not been on evaluation of AFRC, thus, serves as motivation to carry out this present study.

Statement of the Problem

AFRC establishment mission and vision are to curb socio-economic and psychological challenges experiencing by ex-men and women military personnel after retirement from services. Hence, the programme becomes a mandatory programme, a year before retirement for abled and disabled soldiers with a major aim of equipping them with vocational and entrepreneurship training for decent living and an enhanced quality of life after retirement. Partly, to also re-integrate them with civil life.

However, some pertinent questions that keep on re-occurring and lingering on in minds are:

1. Why some ex-soldiers are living in poverty and homeless despite the programme after retirement?
2. Why some ex-soldiers are very aggressive in their relationship with the civil society, redundant, depressed and managing health challenges after their retirement from service?

It was against this foregoing background, the study was carried out.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was on evaluation of Armed Forces Resettlement centres vocational and entrepreneurial training on mitigating psycho-economic challenges of ex-military personnel in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Investigate the impact of AFRC on quality of life among the ex-men and women
2. Ascertain the effectiveness of AFRC in curtailing psychological challenges of some military personnel after post-services in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The results of the study will be significant in the following ways;

Firstly, the findings of the study will enable AFRC provider {Government} to determine whether the mission and vision of the programme are achieved or not.

Moreover, the findings of the study will give room for innovation that will help in effective planning and implementation of the programme. Besides, the findings of the study will enable soldiers, especially, those in active service to know the benefits of AFRC to their well-beings and economic virility after their retirement. Lastly, the study will add to the existing studies on AFRC, thus, becomes a source of reference to researchers in future.

Research Questions

1. Does AFRC programme has impact on quality of life of ex-soldiers after post-service in Nigeria?
2. Is AFRC implementation effective in managing psychological challenges of ex-soldiers in Nigeria?

3. Are ex-soldiers putting the training acquire through AFRC in practicing after retirement in Nigeria?

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Vocational Training

Vocational Training (VT) is a subject of pluralism thus, implies that it has various explanations and meanings. Mullins (2010), described training as a process of systematically acquired job related knowledge, skills and attitudes in order to perform with effectiveness and efficiency specific tasks. Friedman {1982} reported by Erinsakin (2014), stated that vocational training is the provision of skills that will enable individuals to carry out diligently vocational activities, such as, artwork, plumbing, vulcanizing, carpentry, cloth weaving and designing and hosts.

In the contemporary society, globally, the place value of vocational training has been recognized. Adefaye (2005), opined that vocational training would often skills in various vocation which could engender a sustainable economic growth and development. It is a “sine-qua-non” to economic and industrial development of the nations. Vocational training programme in recent times has been attracting the attention of various international agencies, charity organizations, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), religious bodies and governments.

Vocational training is an institutional framework and human capacity building programme socio-economic challenges of individuals and the nations.

Ekon (2010), advanced many factors for participations in vocational training cardinally, which centres on the desire to eradicate poverty and unemployment reduction.

Entrepreneurship Training

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Entrepreneurship training initiative is built on the prosperity it could offers to individuals and the nations. Ogundele, Akingbade and Akinlasi (2012), maintained that entrepreneurship training is very crucial at boosting productivity, motivation, creating employment and prosperity. A corollary exists between entrepreneurship training and improved income generation and wealth creation {Erinsakin 2014:14}. Entrepreneurship training is acquisition of values and competency that would make individuals a successful entrepreneurship. The essence – Entrepreneurship training to Erinsakin 2014:38 is to train would-be entrepreneurs on ability to carry out feasibility study, costing, financial planning, record keeping, business planning and engender the spirit of business innovation and creativity in individuals. Aina (2008), asserted that acquisition of entrepreneurship training will enable individuals to seek investment opportunity profitably.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the research. The population of the study comprised, ex-soldiers in Nigeria. The sample size of the study was three hundred (360) respondents. Ten respondents were selected through a snow-balling sampling technique from each of the Thirty six (36) states of Federation of Republic of Nigeria (FRN). Two research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study.

The research instruments that were used to collect data for the study was constructed by the researchers tagged, “Evaluation on Armed Forces Resettlement Centres Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training on mitigating psycho-Economic challenges among Ex-military Personnel in Nigeria”. It was fashioned on four-point likert ratio scale of Strongly Agreed (SA),

Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) and rated on 4-points; 4:3:2 and 1, respectively and complemented with Four Group Discussions (FGD).

The research instruments were validated by two experts in Test and Measurement while, its reliability was determined through test-retest method at two weeks interval 0.72 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data collected on research questions were analyzed using, descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{X}) while, data generated quantitatively through FGDs were collected, collated and transcribed, qualitatively.

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Presentation of Findings

Research Question: Does AFRC programme has impact on quality of life among ex-soldiers after post-services in Nigeria?

Table I: showing simple percentages, frequency (D units and mean (\bar{X}) on does AFRC programme has impact on quality of life among ex-soldiers in Nigeria.

N= 360, C = 2.5								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N %	MEAN \bar{X}	DECISION
1.	AFRC enhance my incomes generation capacity after post-service	279 77.5	39 10.83	23 6.38	19 5.27	360	3.60	Agreed
2.	AFRC cannot enhance my incomes retirement	3 0.83	41 11.38	39 10.83	277 76.94	360	1.36	Rejected
3.	Training acquired through AFRC gives me economic security	299 83.05	31 8.61	24 6.66	6 1.66	360	3.73	Agreed
4.	AFRC training acquired can't guarantee my economic security	4 1.11	12 3.33	66 18.33	278 77.22	360	1.28	Rejected
5.	Through AFRC training I am gainfully engaging on gainful	291 80.83	37 10.27	13 3.61	19 5.27	360	3.66	Agreed

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	job activities after retirement							
6.	Despite the training acquired through AFRC programme I am still facing with unemployment challenges after retirement	11 3.05	19 5.27	42 11.66	288 80	360	1.31	Rejected
		887	179	207	887		2.50	Agreed
	TOTAL WEIGHT	41.06	8.28	9.58	41.06			

Keys: N = Total number of Respondents, C = cut off point

Mean = \bar{X} , Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed = A, Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD)

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1 above, shows the result on research question due. On item (1) responses obtained indicated; 279 (77.5), 39 (10.83), 23 (6.38) and 19 (5.27) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. In item (2), the following responses were got; 3 (0.83), 41 (11.38), 39 (10.83) and 277 (76.94) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. On item(3), responses got indicated; 299 (83.05), 31 (8.61), 24 (6.66) and 6 (1.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

On item (4), 4 (1.11), 12 (3.33), 16 (18.33) and 278 (27.22) as responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (5), the following responses were got: 29 (80.83), 37 (10.27), 13 (3.61) and 19 (5.27) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Finally, on item (6), responses obtained indicated: 11 (3.05), 19 (5.27), 42 (11.66) and 288 (80) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Generally, speaking this result revealed that the average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is not greater than the mean of average rating scale of ($\bar{X} = 2.5$). This implies that AFRC

programme could positively impact on quality of life of ex-soldiers or military personnel after post-service or retirement.

Research Question Two: Is AFRC implementation effective in managing psychological challenges of ex-soldiers in Nigeria?

Table 2: showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{X}) on is AFRC implementation effective in managing psychological challenges of ex-soldiers in Nigeria.

N = 360, C = 2.5								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N %	MEAN \bar{X}	DECISION
7.	AFRC training enables me to overcome depression after my post – service.	293 81.38	56 15.55	9 2.5	2 0.55	360	3.77	Agreed
8.	Despite training acquired through AFRC, depression is often the case.	8 2.22	32 8.88	51 14.16	259 71.94	360	1.35	Rejected
9.	AFRC training enhances my well-being after my retirement	297 82.5	37 10.27	16 4.44	10 2.77	360	3.72	Agreed
10.	AFRC training does not enhance my well-being after retirement	25 6.94	19 5.27	48 13.33	268 74.44	360	1.44	Rejected
11.	Through AFRC training, I am actively involving in entrepreneurial activities, thus, help me not to be redundant after retirement	301 83.6	23 6.38	17 4.72	19 5.27	360	3.68	Agreed
12.	AFRC training does not make to be involving in entrepreneurial activities thus, heightening my redundancy after post service	14 3.88	18 5.0	29 8.05	299 83.05	360	1.29	Rejected
13.	AFRC training helps me to overcome emotional challenge after retirement	291 80.83	33 9.16	28 7.77	8 2.22	360	3.68	Agreed
14.	Through AFRC, training, I do not experiencing emotional challenge after retirement	19 5.22	33 9.16	42 11.66	266 73.88	360	1.45	Rejected
	TOTAL WEIGHT	1,248 43.48	251 8.74	240 8.36	1,131 39.40		2.54	Agreed

KEYS: N = Total Number of Respondents, C = cut off point, Mean = \bar{X} Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed = A, Disagreed = D = Strongly Disagreed (SD)

Source = Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 above, shows the result on research question two. On item (7), the responses got shows 293 (81.38), 56 (15.55), 9 (2.5) and 2 (0.55) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (8), results indicated, (2.22), 32 (8.88), 51 (14.16) and 259 (71.94) for strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed, disagreed. On item (9), the following responses were obtained, as well; 297 (82.57), 37 (10.27), 16 (4.44) and 10 (2.77) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

On item (10), 25 (6.94), 19 (5.27), 48 (13.33) and 268 (74.44) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed were obtained. On item (11) responses got reveal the following; 30 (83.61), 23 (6.38), 17 (4.72) and 19 (5.27) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (12), the following responses were got 14 (3.88), 18 (50), 29 (8.05) and 299 (83.05) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. The results obtained on item (13) show 291 (80.83), 33 (9.16), 28 (7.77) and 8 (2.22) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

On item (14), the following responses were got; 19 (5.22), 33 (9.16), 42 (11.66) and 266 (73.88) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

The total weight of the result indicated that the average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is lesser than the mean of rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.54$) thus, indicates that AFRC could effectively help to manage psychological challenges of ex-soldiers in Nigeria.

Research Question Three: Are ex-soldiers making use of training acquired through AFRC after retirement?

Table 3: showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{X}) on are ex-soldiers making use of training acquired through AFRC after retirement.

N = 360, C = 2.5								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N %	MEAN (\bar{X})	DESIGN
15.	Since, I have retired, I have been putting training acquired through AFRC into practice	269 74.72	66 18.33	19 5.27	6 1.66	360	3.66	Agreed
16.	I have never make use of training offered by AFRC into use	27 7.5	46 12.77	32 8.88	255 70.83	360	1.56	Rejected
17.	I do acknowledged the AFRC training as beneficial to my condition of living after post-service	266 73.88	48 13.33	13 3.61	33 9.16	360	3.51	Agreed
18.	Training offered by AFRC was add no values to condition living after post-service	10 2.77	37 10.27	69 19.16	244 67.77	360	1.48	Rejected
19.	AFRC training are practicable after retirement	303 84.16	33 9.16	5 1.38	19 5.27	360	3.72	Agreed
20.	AFRC trainings are not practicable after retirement.	12 3.33	2 0.55	47 13.05	299 83.05	360	1.24	Rejected
	Total	887 41.06	232 10.74	185 8.56	856 39.62		2.52	Agreed

Keys: N= \bar{X} , Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed = A, Disagreed = D, Strongly Disagreed = SD

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 3 above shows the responses obtained on research question three. On item (15), the following responses were obtained, 269 (74.72), 66 (18.33), 19 (5.27) and 6 (1.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (16), responses obtained indicated, 27 (7.5), 46 (12.77), 32 (8.88) and 255 (70.83) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly

disagreed. On item (17), 266 (73.88), 48 (13.33), 13 (3.61) and 33 (9.16) were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed, respectively.

On item (18), the following responses were got, 10 (2.77), 37 (10.27), 69 (19.16) and 244 (67.77) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (19), responses offered indicated the following, 303 (84.16), 33 (9.16), 5 (1.38) and 19 (5.27) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Finally, on item (20), responses got revealed, 12 (3.33), 2 (0.55), 47 (13.05) and 299 (83.05) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly agreed, respectively.

On several note, the average rating scale of four ($\bar{X}= 2.5$) is than the mean of rating scale of four ($\bar{X}= 2.52$). The result therefore, indicated that the Nigerian ex-military personnel's in ex-soldiers were making use of both vocational and entrepreneurial training after their post-service or retirement.

Discussion of Results

The result on research question one revealed a positive impact of AFRC programme in vocational and entrepreneurial training on ex-military personnel after post-service. The result is in consonance with the view of Duke (2004) that vocational training could result into living a good life or quality of life. Hence, AFRC programmes offers skills and values to ex-soldiers that could equip them with vibrant productive skills that could enable them to break the yoke of poverty and sustaining them communicably after their retirement. This is also in line with the responses obtained from the discussants summing the FGD session.

FGD – a male retired soldier in Lagos State submits that:

I am skill very useful for myself

I could fetch for my basic needs

Even, when government had not pay

My retirement emolument.

The skills acquired through a year programme

Of AFRC has really assisted me to

Living comfortable after post-services.

Another beneficiary of AFRC programme responded that:

The initiative of the Federal Government

to make the programmes compulsory for

soldiers that are about to retire from

service is a laudable one. Training got

through the programme make life after

retirement an enjoyable one for me.

Training got through the programme have

Be sustaining me economically. Today, I am living fine.

FGD-Ex-Female soldiers in Akwa-Ibom State

The result obtained on research question two is also buttressed by the opinion of Erinsakin (2014), that lack of regular incomes could result into depression, anger, frustration and neutral challenges.

However, all these could be abated if people are equipped with values and skills that could make them to be gainfully employed, self-reliant and have self-security. The opinion or responses got during the FGDs are in consonance with this:

For my years I lived in barrack

Without interaction with the civil society.

Initially, I thought that life after retirement

would be characterized with loneliness

Frustration and depression.

The opposite is the case for me, especially, my training

On entrepreneurship have boost my interaction with

The civil services on business grounds and that has

Been help my initial psychological warmness before

my retirement.

FGD- Male ex-soldiers in Kaduna station

The result on research question time is also in agreement with the submission of some discussants during the FGDs.

I don't know of other colleagues or retirees,

As for me, I have a small business centre

That I am running for my survival after

my retirement from the military service.

FGDs- Male ex-soldiers in Enugu State

Another discussant had this to say:

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Smile, I had retired, I have been

Running a poultry farm.

The above responses from the FGD discussants indicate that ex-soldiers in Nigeria are putting into practice training acquired through the AFRC programme.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study conclusions were made that; AFRC programme enable the retired military personnel in Nigeria to be living a decent life and enhancing quality of life.

Also, the programmes help the retirees from military service to overcome psychological challenges that often associating with the retirees.

Finally, ex-soldiers in Nigeria are putting into practice training acquired through AFRC programme in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusions of the study:

1. The Federal Government of Nigeria should be assisting the ex-soldiers to source too initial capital to embark on vocational and entrepreneurial activities as soon as, they disengage from active services.
2. Government should put in place a good strategy or mechanism of monitoring the retirees (ex-soldiers) on their various vocations after their post-service.
3. The period for the programme should be extended beyond a year. This will give room for an extensive acquisition of the training.

4. The soldiers on the training should be well educated and enlightened on the benefits of the training to their socio-economic and psychological wellness and well-beings after their retirement.
5. The ex-military personnel's retirement enrollment should be paid on time, this will enable them to overcome the problem of borrowing money to stand business or vocational centre and hosts.

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